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The incidence of depression in rheumatoid arthritis

Hummadi GA

Abstract

Objective: To make a systematic survey of depressive symptoms in relation to rheumatoid arthritis (RA) as well as to determine the severity of these symptoms in comparison with other chronic medical patients.

Design: Beck depression inventory, the Arabic version.

Setting: Baghdad Medical City hospital.

Participants: A hundred RA patients were screened. An equal number of patients with chronic medical disorders were taken as a compare group.

Results: 38 patients with RA (38%) met the predetermined criteria for depression, while 33 patients (33%) with chronic medical disorders, reached these criteria. It was found that 23 patients (60.5%) with mild depression, 11 patients (28.9%) with moderated depression ad 4 patients (10.5%) with severe depression in patients with R.A.

Conclusions: depression is not significantly differing in distribution among RA patients as compared with chronic medical patients.

Most of the depressive cases appeared to be of mild severity and more often showed symptoms of fatigability, work retardation, sadness and less suicidal feeling.

Introduction

There have been many reports about depressive manifestations among chronic medical patients, depression is common among them but the diagnosis is frequently missed. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a systemic disease characterized by inflammatory changes in joints and associated structures. There are also a number of extra-articular signs and symptoms [1].

Self-reported pain intensity was more clearly related to disability and reported recent disease activity than to depression [2].

Depression in arthritis is a reaction to loss of function, loss of self-esteem or anticipated losses in the future. The denial of illness in RA patients gives way to anger which is followed by depression any renewed flare may immediately promote anger or depression [3]. The majority of studies that considered depressed mood in patients with RA failed to analyze the relative contribution of psychological, social and disease state variables [4].

Correspondent author:

Ghazi Abboud Hummadi GA
Al Rashad Psychiatric Hospital
Baghdad, Iraq
E-mail: ghazi957@yahoo.com

Patients and Methods

A total of hundred rheumatoid patients were screened. An equal number of patients with chronic medical illnesses including 25 % endocrine disorders, 21 % cardiovascular disorders, 12% respiratory disorders, 11% renal disorders, 10% gastrointestinal disorders, 8% hematological disorders, 6% malignant diseases, 5% liver disorders, and 2% skin disorders were taken as compare group. Both groups were matched for age, sex and marital status. Patients included were between the ages of 20-45 years. Seventy-five patients (75%) of them were females and twenty five patients (25%) of them The RA patients who contributed to this study were attending out-patients clinic of rheumatology of Baghdad Medical City Hospital. They were diagnosed according to 1987 revised American Rheumatism Association criteria for RA. While the non-rheumatoid patients with chronic medical disease were attending outpatients clinic of general medicine in the same hospital.

The instrument used for screening was Beck depression inventory (BDI). 13 clinical features were rated in detail. The Arabic version of the B.D.I. was used which is prepared by Dr. Gareeb, Azhar University, Psychiatric Department (5-6). The severity of depression was determined according to the degree of total scores for each patient. A score of 5 – 7 indicate mild, 8 – 15 moderate, and if 16+ severe depression [6]. The data were gathered and classified according to different variables or factors. were males.

Results:

1- Among the 100 patients with RA observed, 38 patients (38%) scored, 5 or above on B.D.I, so they met the predetermined criteria for depression, while in non-rheumatoid chronic medical patients of the 100 patients, 33 patients (33%) reached the cut-off score or above.

2- Sex variation: Among female patients with RA screened, 29 patients (38.6%) were depressed, while 9 patients (36%) were depressed among males. On the other hand, it was 25 patients (33.3%) among chronic medical female patients and 8 patients (32%) for males.

3- Severity of depression: It was found those 23 patients (60.5%) with mild depression, 11 patients (28.9%) with moderate depression and 4 patients (10.5%) with severe depression in patients with RA, while it was 18 patients (54.5%) with mild depression, 11 patients (33.3%) with moderate depression, and 4 patients (12.12%) with severe depression in patients with non-rheumatoid chronic medical disease.

4- Age: The rheumatoid patients & the compare patients were divided into 3 age groups. The distribution of depression according to these groups is shown in table 1 and 2, respectively.

5- Predominant depressive symptoms: According to the mean score of each symptom, the predominance of depressive symptoms were arranged in hierarchical order for the patients with RA.

Fatigability, pessimism, hopelessness, helplessness, were predominant, while in non-rheumatoid medical patients, work retardation, fatigability, sadness, indecisiveness, pessimism, hopelessness, & dissatisfaction were predominant.

6- Life events & psychiatric history: Recent life events were found in 14 patients (36.8%) of depressed patients with R.A. and in 11 patients (33.3%) of depressed patients with non-rheumatoid medical diseases, where as life events were found in 12 patients (19.3%) of non-depressed patients with R.A. and in 15 patients (22.3%) in medical non-depressed patients.

7- Depression and type of treatment in RA: Depression is more in rheumatoid patients who are on immunosuppressive, penicillamine, and gold therapy, and less depression in patients on steroid therapy.

Table 1: Depression according to the age among patients with RA

Age (yrs)	Total No.	Depression	
		No	%
20 – 29	35	10	28.5
30 – 39	35	13	37.1
40 -45	30	15	50

Table 2: Depression according to the age among patients with non-rheumatoid chronic medical diseases.

Age (yrs)	Total No.	Depression	
		No	%
20 – 29	35	9	25.7
30 – 39	35	11	31.42
40 -45	30	13	43.3

Discussion

The above results have shown that depression is a common phenomenon among rheumatoid and other chronic medical patients. That is 38% among rheumatoid and 33% among non-rheumatoid patients. There is no significant difference in distribution of depression between the two groups. The depression is consistent with that in other studies [1, 7, 8, 9, 10].

A 15 years follow up study of 74 female patients with definite or classic RA was performed during the clinical course of the illness, 40% had depressive reaction[12].

Depression among chronic medical diseases was found to fall with in a range of 22-50% in different studies[7,8,9,10,11].

Most of depression appeared to be of mild severity for rheumatoid and non rheumatoid medical patients which is consistent with that in other studies [7, 13]. In a rural general medical practice, the estimated prevalence of depression was 28.3% for mild & 18.3% for moderate & 8.8 % for severe depression. ([13].

Depression increases with age & this may be related to the fact that psychological mechanisms which permitted coping with stress at an earlier age may have diminished gradually as well as chronicity of illness may play the same role.

The predominant depressive symptoms in rheumatoid and non rheumatoid medical patients were nearly similar apart from more fatigability than work retardation in R.A., the reverse in non-rheumatoid patients.

Work retardation and fatigability may reflect real incapacity and disability of patient due to physical illness. Suicidal thinking and guilty feelings were found little, and this goes with the study of Moffic and Paykel[7].

The life events were found to have more impact in precipitation of depression in depressed patients of both groups. So patients were more likely to have other concurrent stresses and depression was not entirely a consequence of the medical state. Depression is more in Rheumatoid patients who are on immunosuppressive ,penicillamie and gold therapy ,however less depression is reported in patients on steroid therapy .This may be due to the remitting effect of steroid as well as amelioration of effect.

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